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TUMOR REGRESSION IN AN ELDERLY DOG USING THE *VISCUM ALBUM* THERAPY ASSOCIATED WITH INJECTABLE *THUYA OCCIDENTALIS*

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ABSTRACT

Pets are living longer. Consequently, they are more predisposed to diseases with advancing age, to the detriment of the lifestyle to which they are submitted. Sometimes these diseases cannot be treated surgically and/or are difficult to control due to concomitant comorbidities that limit the execution of anesthetic and surgical procedures. Under this perspective, other therapies should be considered to treat these diseases, aiming to control, provide relief, and even cure, such as total remission in cases of various tumors. Homeopathy, a therapy enunciated by Hahnemann, relieves clinical signs, promoting a better quality of life, especially for those who no longer find alternatives in conventional treatments. This study reports the treatment of a tumor in an elderly male dog using oral and injectable homeopathic medicines. The tumor was located in the right lower lip, near the labial commissure, and showed complete remission on April/2020. This patient was followed up until his death in August 2022, with no recurrence of the initial complaint. According to clinical results, the homeopathic therapy was effective in its purpose, reestablishing the patient's health conditions. Despite being an elderly animal and its slow biological response, the treatment was successful.

KEY WORDS

Complementary therapy, tumor, senility.

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Introduction

Cancer is one of the current main public health problems in the world and is among the top four causes of premature death in humans. This disease's incidence and mortality rates are alarming and increasing every day. Aging, environmental contamination, and a high incidence of chronic inflammation have contributed to the higher cancer incidence (BRAY et al., 2018). The canine population is not far from this index, mainly because animals live closer to humans nowadays. Consequently, they inherit human dietary and environmental problems due to increasing daily stress and sedentary lifestyle (author...).

Therefore, cancer is commonly diagnosed (Oliveira, 2016) in veterinary offices worldwide, responsible for considerable morbidity and mortality rates, especially in elderly animals. Most of the time, the treatment of this disease is challenging to manage, and its disappearance without a satisfactory explanation is rarely accepted in the medical world. This process is known as "tumor regression"; in exceptional cases, patients are cured of the initial disease. The incidence of tumor regression is estimated to be between one in 60,000 and one in 140,000 cases of cancer. However, it is not easy to define it based on clinical aspects in humans (Chang, 2000). The medical literature is rich in case reports of neoplasms confirmed by anatomopathological examination, with computed tomography (CT) or magnetic resonance imaging (MRI), and shows generalized diseases with spontaneous regression, which cover almost all histological types of cancer (Grillet et al., 1984).

Thus, complementary therapies are indicated to help patients diagnosed with cancer in their treatments. In this context, Homeopathy has been used to treat various diseases for more than 200 years. This therapy can provoke the diseased organism to reestablishment, stimulating mechanisms similar to those described in the literature responsible for spontaneous regression in cancer patients (Valle & Carvalho, 2021).

Under this perspective, complementary therapies comprise a better way to treat cancer patients, especially those without management possibilities through conventional therapies. This study aims to report a case of tumor regression in an elderly animal with no possibility of surgical removal of the lesion, which was submitted to treatment using injectable homeopathic medicines, showing excellent results.

CASE REPORT

A 16-year-old male dog, Teckel breed, was seen at NaturalPet Veterinary Clinic, in Brasília, Brazil, in April/2020. The dog was neutered two years before the veterinary appointment after diagnosing multiple nodules in the left testicle with no subsequent biopsy. The dog had a history of chronic kidney disease (CKD) in control for three years; the presence of a nodule in the spleen with annual follow-up for two years and no apparent evolution; the presence of severe dental calculus in all teeth with concomitant periodontal disease; and a nodule in the right lower lip (Figure A – I) with intermittent bleeding for approximately eight months. The lip nodule was evaluated by another colleague who considered the impossibility of surgical removal due to the advanced CKD and the patient's age. For this reason, a conservative treatment through antibiotic therapy was chosen. This therapy was successful during its utilization. However, the lesion ulcerated again and increased in size two weeks after the end of the medication. In addition, the owners reported that the animal had sporadic sneezing; eyes with yellowish secretion of bad odor; intermittent insomnia (1-3 am); and intermittent gastrointestinal changes, including sporadically gastrointestinal indisposition when contradicted or anxious. The animal also presented problematic behavior, being cranky, insecure, vengeful, and feeling cold more than usual. On physical examination, the patient appeared to be

slightly disoriented, compatible with the changes described for the cognitive impairment diagnosis. On this occasion, the owners stated that the animal presented compulsive walking, insomnia, and sometimes the patient stopped in front of the wall and could not get out. The patient was hydrated and presented normal colored mucous membranes, artery pressure 13X8, heart rate 110 bpm, temperature 37.4 °C, cardiac auscultation within the normal range for the species, and the presence of a pendulum mass in the medial portion of the right lower lip. Blood was collected for laboratory tests. The treatment protocol comprised the following oral and injectable homeopathic medicines: *Arsenicum album* 30CH, three drops (PO), SID, for 90 days; *Thuya* D9, one ampoule (SC), SID, three times a week for eight weeks; and *Viscum album* D3, one ampoule (SC), SID, in alternate days for 60 days. Every seven days for four weeks, the animal returned to the clinic for application of *Viscum album* D2 (EV) and autohemotherapy.

Results & Discussion

According to Curioni et al. (2021), the exact mechanism responsible for spontaneous tumor remission is unknown. However, according to King et al. (2001), several cases of the cure of malignant neoplasms are described in the literature with no apparent explanation. The most accepted current theories for triggering tumor regression involve infectious and hypoglycemic processes as generators of an exacerbated immune response, responsible for the healing mechanism. Immunomodulation mechanisms may be directly involved in this mechanism, which can be observed as a mutual relationship of cancer with the host, determining a balance between forces or an escape from the immune response (Schreiber et al., 2011). Under ideal conditions, the innate and adaptive elements of the immune system orchestrate together to suppress cancer, making use of regulatory T cells (CD4+), Natural-Killers (NK), cytotoxic T cells (CD8+), dendritic cells, macrophages with a series of secreted proteins such as interferon-gamma, IL-12, and tumor necrosis factor (TNF), that act in harmony. This process caused by the organism results in tumor regression, which can be a manifestation of this dynamic process (Jhawar et al., 2017). One of the keys to better clarifying how the spontaneous remission mechanism works seems to be the activation/stimulation of innate immunity. A series of case reports of tumor remission raised the hypothesis that stimulating an infectious condition helps the innate immune system recognize tumor cells (Niakan, 2019).

The present case report describes the remission of a tumor by injecting the homeopathic medicines *Thuya occidentalis* and *Viscum album*. These medicines were chosen based on the anatomopathological similarity and bidirectional action on tumor cells and the host, stimulating the host's immune system and resulting in a better response to this therapy. A similar immune system activity appears to be caused by the medicines mentioned above, corroborating with the hypotheses of mechanisms of spontaneous tumor remission described by Schreiber et al. (2011) and Niakan (2019). The homeopathic medicine *Arsenicum album* was also administered and was selected according to the pathogenetic similarity because it resembles the physical and mental characteristics of the patient.

The medicine *Viscum album* has been used for more than 200 years by anthroposophic medicine to treat cancer patients with varied types of tumors, showing surprising reports in the literature. In the case reported here, the injectable use of this medicine started in April/2020, with complete tumor remission in four weeks. The animal lived until August/2022 with no major complications and died due to pre-existing kidney disease at treatment initiation, totaling 28 months of uneventful survival. Within this context, *Viscum album* already has established use by human medicine, showing a mechanism of action that can resemble what is supposed to occur in cases of spontaneous remission.

Figure A. I) Lesion aspect at treatment initiation - D0. II and III) Injury primary site showing tumor regression at 60 days of treatment.

Figure B. I, II, and III) Tumor regression due to treatment. The tumor was located in the right lower lip, ventral lateral portion, with globular aspect, not ulcerated. IV and V) Complete reestablishment of the tissue with tumor remission.

Conclusion

It is notorious the ability of the medicines selected in the present case to stimulate the patient's immunity to recognize tumor cells and act against them, causing the host to become immunocompetent. Therefore, the results obtained in this case were highly satisfactory, restoring the patient's overall health condition.

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